

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city: Implications on the quality of education

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Abstract:

This descriptive research design was conducted to determine the status of the increased number of private schools and its proliferation in Marawi City based on the 1998 Revised Manual for Private Education particularly in the compliance of government requirements and its implications to the quality of education. A total of twenty-six private schools served as the respondents of this study. Many developing nations lack adequate resources to fund public schools and universities. Faced with growing lower-and middle-class populations that are too often underserved, these nations increasingly rely upon private education to complement public education. The increase in the number of private schools could be alarming especially when it comes to quality education. Ideally, private schools should always be adjunct to quality education, yet it is sad to note that the prevailing perceptions on the proliferation of private schools are not accompanied by quality. Findings revealed that the relationship between the profile of the school and the extent of compliance with government requirements revealed no correlation at all, while the t-test revealed a not significant relationship between the teachers' profile and the level of passing standardized and board examinations. For the relationship between the profile of the owners'/administrators and the extent of participation in extension and community outreach programs, except for the monthly income was found to have not significant relationship with extension and community outreach programs. Lastly, the test of difference between the owners'/administrators' and teachers' perceptions on the factors for the proliferation of private schools revealed a not significant difference.

Keywords :

private schools, Marawi City, Philippines, proliferation of private schools

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Introduction

Philippine education institutions varied in quality. Some universities were excellent; others were considered “diploma mills” with low standards, especially those in poor rural areas. The area in the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) has been historically disadvantaged relative to the rest of the Philippines, obtaining fewer social and economic benefits and suffering disruptions from armed conflict. As a result, its social and economic indicators are the lowest in the country. About 21 percent of the barangays in the ARMM are without schools. The high drop-out rates and the correspondingly high illiteracy rate- along with conflict and the lack of job-creating investment in the region have contributed to high unemployment.(www.equalls.org/03.07.09/8:38)

Education is very essential to the Filipinos and it is a mandate in the Philippine Constitution. Quality education is an essential element for economic growth, upward social mobility, and competition in the interconnected world economy.

There is growing evidence that private participation in education can improve effectiveness in developing countries in cost-effective manner and without compromising equity. Moreover, a number of studies demonstrate that private participation can encourage the public sector to improve their quality and efficiency. This is brought by the competition among providers of services which causes the lowering of costs and improves responsiveness to the needs of consumers (Journal on Knowledge, Creativity and Transformation of Societies,2007).

The increase in the number of private schools could be alarming especially when it comes to quality education. Ideally, private schools should always be adjunct to quality education, yet it is sad to note that the prevailing perceptions on the proliferation of private schools are not accompanied by quality.

Thus, this study was conducted to determine the status of the increased number of private schools and its proliferation in Marawi City based on the 1998 Revised Manual for Private Education particularly in the compliance of government requirements and its implications to the quality of education.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

This study is best to examine from multiple perspective anchored from its underpinning theories which give basis to the interrelated factors for the proliferation of private schools in particular in Marawi City.

This study takes into consideration the Functionalist Theory and the Conflict Theory. Functionalism is a social paradigm that views society as a system of interdependent parts, or subsystems. For the functionalist, education is an institution that functions to fulfill the needs of the society and that education exists to impart knowledge to the students that they will need to function in everyday life.

The functionalists’ three broad functions are socialization, skills provision, and role allocation. Durkheim and Talcott Parsons (2009), another functionalist theorist saw

education as an essential agency of socialization whose function is to transmit common values to the next generation.

In the idea of conflict theory, it is rooted from Karl Marx, the great German and political activist. The people that hold powers are the ones who have control of what are perceived as scarce resources, like money, land, political influenced and education (www.grinnell.edu/courses/soc/IntroTheories/Conflict.html/03.08.09/9:33). This theory implies that educational institutions serve the interest of those who dominate the economy, namely the upper class, and not all social groups may have the same level of access to education.

Expounding on this theory, those parents who can afford to pay the cost of private schools would likely benefit from the quality of education offered by the private schools while those with much lower income could not do otherwise.

Elaborating further on the conflict theory and the commodification of education, education is a special product in a sense that it is meant to increase the production of wealth for the future.

Another theory is the political-economy theory in the determination of education funding and quality (De la Croix and Doepke, 2007). This theory suggests that the structure of the political system has effects with the quality of education offered by public schools thereby benefiting the private schools in return. The quality of public schooling, in turn, is determined through a political-economy mechanism whereby the government is responsive with the needs of the public school sectors.

There are many indicators of quality education. For this study, it explored four important elements that could lead to its attainment. These four elements are: (1) physical; (2) human elements; (3) quality content; and (4) quality outcomes.

Related Studies

A number of researchers were found to be value and relevant to the present investigation. One was the case study conducted by Tooley and Gulosino (2000) found that private schools in many depressed suburban and rural areas are charging minimal fees yet offering quality education. Even low-income families are responding to the perceived inadequate and poorly managed public schools by sending their children to private schools instead. Private schools are able to maximize available resources in their immediate environment whether they operate at low end profits or purely as a non-profit association.

Additionally, in the study of Jimenez (1991) on the relative efficiency of private schools in some developing countries such as the Philippines, Colombia, Dominican Republic, Tanzania and Thailand resulted that private schools generally outperform public school students on standardized math and language tests. This finding holds even after accounting for the fact that, on average, private school students in these countries come from more advantaged backgrounds than their public school counterparts.

The question on whether private schools provide a better education than public schools depends largely upon the student background. Thus, the ratio of relative effectiveness to relative cost is consistently greater than one. These results indicate that private schools are more efficient than public schools, at least for secondary schools in the sample countries. The findings of the study have more implications on policy. Over restrictive regulations on private schools (including outright prohibition in some countries) may be suppressing an efficient way to provide education.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive research design in the analysis and interpretation of data on the profile of the respondents and the status of the private schools in Marawi City. An initial survey was conducted for the listing of the private schools and their physical profile.

A total of twenty-six private schools served as the respondents of this study. The data gathered were analyzed using the statistical tools such as frequency, percentage and weighted mean (WM). For the establishment of relationship among variables used and the testing of perception difference among the respondents, Pearson Product Moment Co-efficient of Correlation and t-test were used. Additionally, this study was conducted in Marawi City which is the center and premier urban center of the province of Lanao del Sur. Furthermore, the respondents of this study are the school owners, administrators and teachers of the various private schools in Marawi City as of Academic Year 2008-2009. The following table shows the List of Private Schools in Marawi City with their Corresponding Population and Sample Size.

Table 1
List of Private Schools in Marawi City with their Corresponding Population and Sample Size

Name of Private School	Owners/Administrators		Teachers	
	Population Size	Sample Size	Population Size	Sample Size
Philippine Integrated School	4	3	50	17
Ibn Siena Integrated School	4	3	120	42
Al Khwarizmi International College	2	2	5	2
MasiricampoAbantas Memorial Science Academy	6	5	18	6
Ranao Child Development Center	2	2	16	6
BubongMarzok Memorial College	2	2	8	3
Cali Paramedical College Foundation	2	2	20	7

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

Dansalan Polytechnic College	3	2	10	3
Datu Mala – Muslim Mindanao Islamic College	3	2	29	10
JamiatuMarawi Al-Islamia Foundation	4	3	36	12
Jamiatu Muslim Mindanao	4	3	25	9
Jamiatul Philippine Al-Islamia	4	3	102	35
Lake Lanao College	2	2	49	17
Lanao Islamic Paramedical College Foundation	3	2	17	6
Mapandi Memorial College	5	4	54	19
Marawi Capitol College Foundation Inc.	4	3	27	9
Mindanao Islamic Computer College	3	2	20	7
Pacasum College	3	2	15	5
Philippine Muslim Teachers College	3	2	8	3
Senator Ninoy Aquino College Foundation	11	9	37	13
Philippine Engineering Agro Industrial College Inc.	3	2	15	5
Marawi Foundation Academy	3	2	16	6
Aba Al Khair Integrated of Lanao Institute	2	2	29	10
Shapiya Integrated School	2	2	13	5
HOPE Healthcare Training Institute	1	1	9	3
Children’s Learning Center	2	2	8	3
Total	87	71	756	262

This study made use of a researcher-made questionnaire patterned from other researches with similar purpose and validated in other groups prior to its actual distribution to the actual respondents. The questionnaire consists of three parts. Part I sought to gather information on the factors/reasons for the proliferation of private schools in Marawi City based on religious, cultural, social, economic and political factors. Part II focused on the status of the private schools which includes their profile as well as those of the owners/administrators and teachers. Part III explored the extent of performance of the private schools based on their compliance with government requirements, passing of standardized and board examinations.

Results and Discussion

The main goal of this study is to determine the status of the increased number of private schools and its proliferation in Marawi City based on the 1998 Revised Manual for Private Education particularly in the compliance of government requirements and its implications to the quality of education.

The data were presented in five parts. The first part focused in the status of the private schools which includes the profile of the schools, the owners/administrators and the teachers. The second part deal with factors for the proliferation of private schools in Marawi City for the school year 2008-2009. The third part deals with the school performance. The fourth determined the relationship between the status of the private schools and their extent of performance and the fifth part discussed the difference between the owners/administrators and teachers perceptions on the factors/reasons for the proliferation of private schools. The following are the major findings of the data analysis.

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Private School's type of Operation

Types of Operation	Frequency	Percentage
With permit from CHED/DepEd/TESDA	44	62.00
Recognized by foreign agency	2	2.80
Others (with permit/registration from either CHED/DepEd/TESDA/SEC	25	35.20
Total	71	100%

The finding then is considered a positive effort of the school operators. This means that they are law-abiding by securing the necessary permit for them to operate and granting them the legal personality. In addition, the registration obtained by the school from the SEC provides security to the juridical personality of the school for the protection of its properties. This means also that the school wants to strengthen its corporate capability by maintaining a regulatory system set by the Commission.

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Private Schools' Type of Organization

Type of Organization	Frequency	Percentage
Single Proprietorship	20	28.20
Partnership	12	16.90
Foundation	30	42.30
Non-Stock Non-Profit	2	2.80
Profit-Oriented, Stock Corporation	7	9.90
Total	71	100%

The finding stresses how school operators prefer to be organized as a foundation because of its versatile structure that could be registered as a company but without shareholders and bound by the founder's intentions not contrary to law. This is linked with the characteristics of a foundation and inclined to charitable activities that benefit

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

the schools in outsourcing financial support. Another advantage of a private foundation is the special consideration afforded it by the government through tax exemptions.

Table 4
Frequency and percentage Distribution of the Private Schools' Type of Curricula Adopted

Type of Curricula Adopted	Frequency	Percentage
Integrated	31	43.70
Secular	27	38.00
Non-Secular	13	18.30
TOTAL	71	100%

This finding supports the growing preference of parents in integrated schools over secular and non-secular schools. This is an influence of the success of some integrated schools founded in Marawi City especially preschool, elementary and high school levels. One of the popular integrated schools favored by most parents for its quality is the Ibn Siena Integrated School (ISIS). The ISIS phenomenon may be considered the first venture to implement a curriculum on integrated education. The integrated curriculum as implemented in the ISIS is inspired by the global trend on the Islamization of knowledge.

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Private Schools According to their Program of Offerings

Program Offerings	Frequency	Percentage
Pre-school, Elementary and Secondary	23	32.40
Preschool and Tertiary	2	2.80
Vocational	2	2.80
Tertiary	8	11.30
All of the above	36	50.70
Total	71	100%

The data show that the common program levels being offered are that of preschool and secondary. Preschools are very much in demand and it is where quality education should start. It is generally observed that parents are presently aware of the importance of early start in education through preschool. The crowding in the secondary levels may be attributed to the subsidy from government and this assistance plays a major role in the operation of the schools in support to the tuition fees collected.

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Private Schools' Physical Structure

Physical Structure	Frequency	Percentage
Type of Building		
Fully Concrete	58	81.70
Semi Concrete	13	18.30

Total	71	100%
Mode of Acquiring the Building		
Owned	35	49.30
Rented	17	23.90
Purchased	19	26.80
Total	71	100%

It has been generally observed that most buildings in Marawi City are fully concreted in both public and privately-owned buildings. The superior protection offered by these concrete buildings against cold climate, storms and criminal intentions make it ideal for learning. In addition, the concrete buildings have high level resistance to fire and noise. In Marawi City, most of the private school buildings are personally owned. It is easier for a school to be established and be registered if the buildings are owned by the school operators themselves. Bigger classroom capacity is much preferred and designed for multipurpose activities. Inasmuch as most of the private schools do not have enough space for auditoriums or function halls, classrooms are designed as a convertible to function halls for general meetings, symposiums, seminars and parties.

Table 7
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Private Schools’ Source of Funds

Source of Funds	Frequency	Percentage
Enrolment and Tuition Fees	28	39.43
Enrolment, Tuition and subsidy for the Government	34	47.90
Fund Assistance/Contribution from Local Sponsors, NGO’s and PO’s	5	7.04
Enrolment, Tuition and Income Generating Projects	4	5.63
Total	71	100%

Enrolment and tuition fees alone are not sufficient for the entire operation of the schools, thus there is a need for financial assistance from the government and NGO’s such as the Fund Assistance to Private Education (FAPE) to standardize the school programs and related support services and the Government Assistance to Students and Teachers in Private Education(GASTPE) Program that aids needy secondary students left out by the public school system’s limited facilities and driven to enroll in private institutions.

Table 8
Mean Ratings of the Private Schools’ Achievement of their Mission, Vision, Goals and Objectives

Key Factors/Areas	Owners/Administrators		Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
Religious mission, vision, goals and objectives	3.46	Fully Achieved	2.73	Almost Achieved

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

Cultural mission, vision, goals and objectives	3.30	Fully Achieved	2.94	Almost Achieved
Social mission, vision, goals and objectives	3.15	Almost Achieved	2.70	Almost Achieved
Economic mission, vision, goals and objectives	3.06	Almost Achieved	2.66	Almost Achieved
Political mission, vision, goals and objectives	2.89	Almost Achieved	2.57	Almost Achieved
Average Weighted Mean	3.17	Almost Achieved	2.72	Almost Achieved

As gleaned in Table 8, both owners/administrators and teacher respondents revealed the same perceptions as to the schools; achievement of their mission, vision, goals and objectives in the religious and cultural aspects as fully achieved, while teachers in most schools rated all aspects as almost achieved in their MVGO. This indicates that these private schools are committed to a shared purpose and direction by defining clear expectations for student learning based on the realistic capability of what their schools could offer.

TABLE 9
Means Ratings of the Private Schools' Adequacy of School Facilities, Equipment and Services

School Facilities, Equipment and Services	Weighted Mean	Description	Rank
Classrooms	3.56	Condition is very good and functioning very well	
Blackboards	3.48	Condition is very good and functioning very well	
Chairs	3.41	Condition is very good and functioning very well	
Toilet	3.17	Condition is good and functioning fairly well	
Water Supply	3.11	Condition is good and functioning fairly well	
Working Tables	3.05	Condition is good and functioning fairly well	
Canteen	2.94	Condition is good and functioning fairly well	
Library	2.78	Condition is good and functioning fairly well	
Praying Room	2.69	Condition is good and functioning fairly well	
Computers	2.67	Condition is good and functioning fairly well	
Reading Corners	2.47	Condition is limited and functioning poorly	

Clinic With Medical Attendant	2.25	Condition is limited and functioning poorly	
Sports Complex	2.06	Condition is limited and functioning poorly	
Cooking/Baking Equipment	1.94	Condition is limited and functioning poorly	
Sewing Equipment	1.42	Condition is missing and is needed	
Average Weighted Mean	2.73	Condition is good and functioning fairly well	

The findings imply a condition which needs more improvement and maintenance to achieve a better equipped school and delivery of quality services. It was noticed that some of the facilities and services considered very important in a school like clinic with medical attendants and sports complex were found to be limited and functioning poorly. These could have a negative bearing on the school in terms of monitoring and securing the health of the students as well as in promoting and sports. The limited conditions of the cooking/baking equipment and the absence of sewing equipment could be an opportunity missed for the students to learn skills which could train them for future livelihood activities. This finding is might be odd.

Table 10
Mean Rating of the Private Schools' Adequacy of their Instructional Materials

Instructional Materials	Weighted Mean	Description	Rank
Print			
Books	2.52	Instructional materials are available and functioning fairly well	5
Magazines, Newspapers, Journals and Articles	2.44	Instructional materials are limited and functioning poorly	7
Cardboards/Flashcards	2.83	Instructional materials area available and functioning fairly well	1
Materials for Project Development	2.60	Instructional Materials are available and functioning fairly well	2
Globe, Maps, Atlas, Human Anatomy Posters and other Science Posters	2.56	Instructional materials is available and functioning fairly well	3
Electronics			
Audio-Visual aids (TV's,DVD's/VCD's/Component)	2.53	Instructional materials and functioning fairly well	4
Computer Assisted instruction	2.51	Instructional materials are limited and functioning poorly	6

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

Equipment			
Sport equipment (ball games, badminton, nets, ring, etc.)	2.35	Instructional materials are limited and functioning poorly	8
Musical Instruments (Drum Sets, piano, guitar etc.)	2.03	Instructional materials are limited and functioning poorly	10
Science Laboratory Equipment (General Lab ware, Physics equipment, biology Equipment, Chemistry Equipment, etc.)	2.12	Instructional materials are limited and functioning poorly	9
Average Weighted Mean	2.44	Instructional materials are limited and functioning poorly	
Standard Deviation	0.38		

These finding suggest that school owners/administrators should give more attention to the procurement of instructional materials for use in their respective schools. Although the school facilities, equipment and service were perceived to be good and functioning fairly well, this can affect the teaching-learning effectiveness of the teachers and students. Instructional materials are educationally important and that the consequences of not having them are particularly harsh in a high-stakes.

B. Profile of the Owners/Administrators and the Teachers

Table 11

Frequency and Percentage of the Owners'/Administrators' and Teachers' Age

Age	Owners/Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
20 – 30 years old	13	18.30	175	66.80
31 – 40 years old	15	21.11	72	27.50
41 – 50 years old	27	38.00	15	5.70
51 years old and above	16	22.50		
Total	71	100%	262	100

The results indicate that majority of the owners/administrators were between 41 to 50 years old, considered to be the prime stage of career development where one is more committed to and stable in their jobs. For the teachers, the findings indicate that the teachers in the private schools of Marawi City are fresh graduates and young.

Table 12
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Owners'/Administrators' and Teachers
Civil Status

Civil Status	Owners/Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Single	9	12.68	128	48.90
Married	58	81.70	130	49.60
Separated	1	1.40	4	1.50
Widow	3	4.22		
Total	71	100%	262	100%

The civil status of the respondents indicates their level of maturity and responsibility brought about by the experiences they have gained through their status. These imply that they are experienced and responsible, fit to be administrators and teachers.

Table 13
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Owners'/Administrators' and Teachers'
Monthly Income

Monthly Income	Owners'/Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
P10,000 and below	26	36.00	254	96.90
P11,000 – P15,000	16	22.50	8	3.10
P16,000 – P20,000	7	9.90		
P21,000 and above	22	31.00		
Total	71	100%	262	100%

The low salaries are take home-pay that the administrators and teachers earn are just an indication of the global economic crisis everyone is facing today. It implies that school reform are further hampered by the low salaries that the respondents receiving especially the teachers. Because of the high rate of unemployment, school teachers and administrators as well suffer from the economic recession.

Table 14
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Owners'/Administrators and Teachers'
Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Owners/Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
College Graduate	11	15.50	179	68.33
With Master's Unit	23	32.40	63	24.04
Master's Degree	22	31.10	20	7.63
Doctoral Degree	15	21.1		
Total	71	100%	262	100%

For the owners/administrators, the data imply that majority were equipped with sufficient academic backgrounds in taking responsibility of their positions. The teacher

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

respondents likewise showed the majority were mostly fresh graduates seeking experiences though initial teaching in private schools.

Table 15
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Owners/Administrators and Teachers' College/University Graduated

College or University Graduated	Owners/Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
University	50	70.40	188	71.80
University/College	21	29.60	74	28.20
Total	71	100%	262	100%

These results suggest that the respondents are academically-trained from the universities. Graduating from the universities may have more advantages considering that they are institutions of higher learning.

Table 16
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Owners'/Administrators' and Teachers' Length of Services

Length of Service	Owners/Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 year	11	15.50	109	41.60
1 – 5 years	8	11.30	103	39.30
6 – 10 years	26	36.60	45	17.20
11 – 15 years	11	15.50	5	1.90
16 – 20 years	2	2.80		
21 years and above	13	18.30		
Total	71	100%	262	100%

The length of service of the respondent is perceived to be associated with experience and commitment. The longer the length of service, the more dedication and commitment is expected in their work. This may also mean sacrifices for the sake of loyalty.

Table 17
Mean Distribution of the Teachers' Teaching Strategies Used

Teaching Strategies	Weighted Mean	Description	Rank
Cooperative Learning	3.23	Teaching Strategy is sometimes used	3
Creative Response	3.25	Teaching Strategy is sometimes used	2
Demonstration	3.23	Teaching Strategy is sometimes used	3
Discovery Learning	2.99	Teaching Strategy is sometimes used	6
Discussion/Debate	3.11	Teaching Strategy is sometimes used	4
Experiential Learning	2.68	Teaching Strategy is	8

		sometimes used	
Integrated Instruction	3.00	Teaching Strategy is sometimes used	5
Field Trip	1.81	Teaching Strategy is rarely used	13
Hands-on	2.56	Teaching Strategy is sometimes used	9
Inquiry	2.70	Teaching Strategy is sometimes used	7
Laboratory	2.07	Teaching Strategy is rarely used	11
Lecture	3.37	Teaching Strategy is always used	1
Model & Simulation	1.51	Teaching Strategy is never used	14
Multimedia Instruction	1.98	Teaching Strategy is rarely used	12
Module	2.16	Teaching Strategy is rarely used	10
Average Weighted Mean	2.64	Teaching Strategy is sometimes used	

The finding also suggested that a positive approach of the teachers was gained to try a other teaching strategies in stimulating the interest of the learners and to motivate them to participate in the learning process.

Part II. Factors/Reasons for the Proliferation of the Private Schools.

Table 18
Religious Factors for the Proliferation of Private Schools

Religious Factors	Owners/Administrators		Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Weighted Mean	Weighted Mean	Description
The establishment of some integrated schools provides fundamental knowledge of Islam and motivates students to become more responsible believers in Islam.	4.45	Very Strong Agreement	4.54	Very Strong Agreement
To develop a well-rounded Muslim personality train with skills and appropriate experiences for gainful living.	4.46	Very Strong Agreement	4.38	Very Strong Agreement
To provide quality education for the youth towards building a progressive Islamic society.	4.59	Very Strong Agreement	4.29	Very Strong Agreement
To provide authentic Islamic as an aid to the traditionally passed knowledge	4.23	Very Strong Agreement	4.26	Very Strong Agreement

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

from the past generations.				
To promote a liberal and tolerant view of religious difference in the world.	4.03	Fair Agreement	4.01	Fair Agreement
Average Weighted Mean	4.35	Very Strong Agreement	4.30	Very Strong Agreement

As indicated, the owners/administrators had very strong agreement on the reasons presented such as to provide fundamental knowledge of Islam and to motivate students to become more responsible believers of Islam; to develop a well/rounded Muslim personality, trained with skills and appropriated experiences for gainful living; to provide quality education for the youth towards building a progressive Islamic society; and to provide authentic Islamic knowledge as an aid traditionally passed knowledge from past generations.

Acquisition of knowledge was a characteristic feature of the Islamic civilization. Even in the early modern times, Muslim thinkers and leaders realized the importance of education in the progress of the Muslim Community particularly, in strengthening the community against the socio-economic and cultural should be defined in relation to the spiritual reality of man and that the proper revival of the Muslims should start not just with great emphasis on education, but with greater emphasis on the right conception of knowledge starting from the college level all the way down to secondary and primary levels (Daud, 1998).

**Table 19
Cultural Factors/Reasons for the proliferation of Private Schools**

Cultural Factors/Reasons	School Owners/ Administrators		Teachers	
	WM	Description	WM	Description
It is through various forms of schooling that the next adult generation can gain insights and understanding of their cultural traditions; values norms and practices.	3.80	Fair Agreement	4.14	Fair Agreement
The presence of many schools helps in the promotion and preservation of the Meranao culture by retaining students especially the women within the confines of Marawi City.	3.97	Fair Agreement	4.01	Fair Agreement
Education through formal schooling guarantees the continuation of culture because of the curriculum that reflects the norms and values which can	3.94	Fair Agreement	4.11	Fair Agreement

strengthen the cultural identity of the learners.				
Schools can facilitate or enhance the sustenance and promotion of cultural varieties through their non-formal or extra-curricular activities.	3.90	Fair Agreement	4.14	Fair Agreement
Schools can be effective partners and agents for the actual performance and observance of cultural norms, values and practices in the community	4.13	Fair Agreement	4.20	Fair Agreement
Average Weighted Mean	3.95	Fair Agreement	4.12	Fair Agreement

Both results implied fair agreement that culture influences the proliferation of private schools.

Formal Schooling now becomes the main instrument for the transmission of culture to generations while at the same time stimulate and develop the intellect and creativity of learners.

Table 20
Social Factors/Reasons for the Proliferation of Private Schools

Social Factors/Reasons	School Owners/ Administrators		Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
Education helps improve the quality of life of the Meranao by promoting attitudinal changes conducive to development.	4.39	Very Strong Agreement	4.29	Very Strong Agreement
The expansion of opportunities provided by the schools to rural and urban poor such as foreign languages, culturally unfamiliar values and ideas aside from everyday life realities promotes permanent literacy.	3.83	Fair Agreement	3.85	Fair Agreement
The presence of many schools can boost the living condition of the people by compensating home and environmental disadvantages	3.87	Fair Agreement	4.05	Fair Agreement

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

through combination of nutritional, health, recreational and educational activities for the youth.				
Education helps young people face the challenges in search for their personal, professional and social identity in the society.	4.45	Very Strong Agreement	4.45	Very Strong Agreement
Schools can also be a key factor for initiating change in the promotion of a more sanitary and hygienic environment in the community.	4.49	Very Strong Agreement	4.33	Very Strong Agreement
Average Weighted Mean	4.20	Fair Agreement	4.19	Fair Agreement

These results imply very strong agreement on social factors' influence on the proliferation of private schools.

**Table 21
Economic Factors/Reasons for the Proliferation of Private Schools**

Economic Factors	Schools Owners/ Administrators		Teachers	
	WM	Description	WM	Description
Establishment of private schools is a profitable business and can increase the income of the owners / stockholders.	3.51	Fair Agreement	3.46	Fair Agreement
Through education and in producing graduates, can improve the opportunity for employment domestic or foreign.	3.85	Fair Agreement	3.85	Fair Agreement
The schools provide opportunity for the students to actively participate in productive economic activities relevant to community basic needs/	4.23	Very Strong Agreement	4.07	Fair Agreement
Schools can be an instrument in coping with the fast changing face of technology affecting the satisfaction of human needs.	3.93	Fair Agreement	3.89	Fair Agreement

The schools can help uncover the unknown natural resources available in the community and maximizes their economic utility by providing ways and means to the production of goods and services based on the available know how and skills.	4.18	Fair Agreement	3.79	Fair Agreement
	3.94	Fair Agreement	3.81	Fair Agreement

These results imply how the economy influences the establishment of schools by equipping the Meranao students with skills and knowledge that will enhance their productivity and creativity in entrepreneurship and technological advancement and participate in the global economy. This supports the study conducted in United Nations Emergency Children Fund (www.kurangayu.com/3.13.09/12:30) which revealed that economic returns from education are higher than most other kinds of investments.

Table 22
Political Factors for the Proliferation of Private Schools

Political Factors	School Owners/ Administrators		Teachers	
	WM	Description	WM	Description
The presence of many schools will help in the political maturity of the people in the conduct of good governance and in the selection of good leader through exercising voting and other political rights responsibly.	3.79	Fair Agreement	3.69	Fair Agreement
It is through education that the Meranao are given the opportunities for their own self-advancement and participate actively in national affairs	4.03	Fair Agreement	4.26	Very Strong Agreement
The presence of many schools will help provide educated citizens who would be able to think and consider more critically about the country's political policies and participate actively in political development of their societies or communities.	3.90	Fair Agreement	3.82	Fair Agreement
The school can train local citizenry to develop the independent decision making as a	4.15	Fair Agreement	3.97	Fair Agreement

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

means for self-determination.				
Through education, students are introduced to a comparative approach in the analysis of the legal, Islamic and traditional rights.	4.24	Very Strong Agreement	4.06	Fair Agreement
Average Weighted Mean	4.02	Fair Agreement	3.96	Fair Agreement

The political factor for the proliferation of private schools is shown in Table 22. The table revealed fair agreement from the respondents. The Average Weighted mean for the owners/administrators was 4.02 while the teacher respondents were 3.96.

Like the other factors, these results imply that politics has strongly influenced the proliferation of private schools with the aim of inculcating values, attitudes and skills which would help the young grow up into “mature” or effective citizens. This could also be linked with the interest of the Meranao towards politics as observed during elections and other political exercises.

Part III. Extent of School Performance

Table 23
Mean Distribution of the School by their Compliance to Government Requirements

Government Requirements	Owners/Administrators		Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
Securing permit to operate	3.87	Always Complied	3.70	Always Complied
Inspection and renewal of permit to operate.	3.70	Always Complied	3.66	Always Complied
Hiring and retention of teachers with professional licenses.	3.55	Always Complied	3.21	Sometimes Complied
Hiring and retention of non-license teachers	2.89	Sometimes Complied	2.76	Sometimes Complied
Implementation of 70-20-10 schemes of revenue allocation and tuition fee increase.	2.76	Sometimes Complied	2.39	Rarely Complied
Average Weighted Mean	3.35	Always Complied	3.14	Sometimes Complied

As indicated by the data in Table 23, private schools in Marawi City comply with the necessary requirements to operate. These schools also recruit both licensed and non-licensed teachers. There is a clear difference in the responses of the owners/administrators and teachers as to the implementation of the 70-20-10 scheme revenue allocation. Implementing this scheme would mean a lot to the teachers and the

students who will be benefited by the 20% allocation intended for school improvement. On the other hand, non-compliance with these requirements would deprive students and teachers in school upgrading or accreditation

Table 24
Mean Ratings of the Schools in their Level of Passing in Standardized or Board Examination

Program Level	Owners/Administrators		Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
Elementary level	3.27	Very Satisfactory	2.84	Very Satisfactory
Secondary or High School Level	3.25	Very Satisfactory	2.67	Very Satisfactory
Vocational/Technical Courses	3.18	Very Satisfactory	2.47	Satisfactory
Tertiary Level	2.50	Satisfactory	2.28	Satisfactory
Average Weighted Mean	3.05	Very Satisfactory	2.56	Very Satisfactory

The result implies that students' performance in standardized examinations such as National Achievement Test, High School Readiness Test and other Board Examinations regulated by the PRC are perceived to be very satisfactory. The selected private schools have shown very satisfactory performance compared with their counterparts in the public schools in the national examinations. Some of these schools are Ibn Sienna Integrated School, MasiricampoAbantas Memorial Science Academy, Dansalan College Foundation Inc., Senator Ninoy Aquino Foundation, JamiatuMarawi Al-Islamia, Marawi Capitol College Foundation and JamiatuMarawi Al-Islamia. For the college level, the Philippine Muslim Teachers College is one of the schools with very satisfactory performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers, 7 out of 10 graduates who took the LET pass the examination.

However, measuring the quality of education does not lie solely on achievement tests and examinations as these have set limitations on the part of the students on what they should learn. Assessment can help everyone understand how students learn best under which conditions and with what knowledge/skills they need to learn more.

Table 25
Mean Ratings of the Respondents by their Researches and Publications

Researches and Publications	Owners/Administrators		Rank	Teachers		Rank
	Weighted Mean	Description		Weighted Mean	Description	
Gazette	1.92	Rarely	7	2.03	Rarely	6

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

Socio-economic	2.07	Rarely	5	2.33	Rarely	3
Science researches	2.25	Rarely	3	2.40	Rarely	2
Literary publication	2.35	Rarely	2	2.50	Rarely	1
Culture and Arts	2.38	Rarely	1	2.01	Rarely	8
Gender Development Studies	1.96	Rarely	6	2.05	Rarely	7
Politics and Governance	1.86	Rarely	8	2.09	Rarely	5
Local Studies	2.13	Rarely	4	2.20	Rarely	4
Average Weighted Mean	2.11	Rarely Studied or Published		2.20	Rarely Studied or Published	

The infrequent conduct of research studies and publications could have a negative impact on the quality of education of the private schools in terms of advancement and accreditation. In all aspects, research work is beneficial. Encouraging the teachers and students to do research studies would promote scholarly and scientific approach in learning process. The same with school publications, this promotes rapport between the administrators, teachers and students by airing issues concerning the school.

Table 26

Mean Ratings of the Schools' Extension Services and Community Outreach Programs

Extension Services and Community Outreach Program	Owners/Administrators		Rank	Teachers		Rank
	Weighted Mean	Description		Weighted Mean	Description	
Summer Bridge Program	2.68	Sometimes	2	2.59	Sometimes	2
Student Volunteer Programs	1.99	Rarely	11	2.02	Rarely	10
Youth Sports Programs	2.27	Rarely	6	2.44	Rarely	5
Health Programs and Medical Missions	2.35	Rarely	5	2.10	Rarely	8
Micro enterprising and Livelihood Training Programs	2.00	Rarely	10	1.82	Rarely	12
Environmental Resource Management Programs	2.13	Rarely	7	1.99	Rarely	11
Food Security Programs	2.01	Rarely	9	2.04	Rarely	9

Skills Development Training	2.56	Sometimes	3	2.50	Rarely	4
Culture and Arts Preservation	2.75	Sometimes	1	2.56	Sometimes	3
Politics and Governance	2.03	Rarely	8	2.19	Rarely	7
Security/Peace and Order	2.68	Sometimes	2	2.63	Sometimes	1
Planning and Rural Concerns	2.45	Rarely	4	2.28	Rarely	6
Average Weighted Mean	2.32	Rarely		2.26	Rarely	

The participation of a school in extension or community outreach program is an indispensable component of a quality school. The lack of involvement would have a negative impact on the performance of the other function of the school as a social institution. This kind of community outreach program is very timely with the current demands of our society. Participating in such programs would be beneficial to the administrators, teachers and students in widening their experiences and knowledge and would help them grow professionally.

Table 27
The Relationship Between the School Profile and the Extent of Compliance with Government Requirements

Compliance with Government Requirements School Profile	R	Analysis of r	T-Test of Significance	Interpretation
Type of Operation	0.0582	No Correlation	1.063854	Not significant accept Ho ¹
Type of Organization	0.018	No Correlation	0.328522	Not significant accept Ho ¹
Type of Curricula Adopted	0.0286	No Correlation	0.522115	Not significant accept Ho ¹
Program Offerings	0.04	No Correlation	0.730516	Not significant accept Ho ¹
Type of building	0.021	No Correlation	0.383299	Not significant accept Ho ¹
Mode of Acquiring the building	0.0168	No Correlation	0.306615	Not significant, accept Ho ¹
Classroom Capacity	0.0308	No Correlation	0.562314	Not significant, accept Ho ¹
Schools Source of Fund	0.0576	No Correlation	1.052849	Not significant, accept Ho ¹

As shown, there is no relationship established between compliance with government requirements and the school profile in the terms of type of operation, type of

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

organization, type of curricula adopted, program offerings, type of building, mode of acquiring the building, classroom capacity and school's source of funds.

This signifies that private schools in Marawi City, regardless of the status of its profile do comply with the requirements set by the government for them to operate. These also imply that school owners give priority to compliance with government requirements like securing the necessary permit to operate from authorized government agencies, the DepEd, CHED, and TESDA is especially important for the schools receiving fund assistance or subsidy from the government. Failure to comply with the requirements would mean delay or suspension of the financial assistance.

Table 28
The Relationship Between the Teachers' Profile and the Level of Passing in Standardized and Board Examination

Teachers Profile Passers to Examination	r	Analysis of r	T-Test of Significance	Interpretation
Elementary	0.078	No Correlation	1.209536	Not significant accept Ho ²
Secondary /High School	0.081333	No Correlation	1.2773	Not significant accept Ho ²
Vocational	0.077167	No Correlation	0.944756	Not significant accept Ho ²
Tertiary/College	0.058833	No Correlation	0.75933	Not significant accept Ho ²

The relationship between the teachers' profile and the level of passing in standardized and board examinations is presented in Table 28. The data revealed that there is no relationship established between the two variables in all program levels from tertiary/college down to the elementary level.

These results imply that the age, civil status, monthly income, educational attainment, school graduated and length of service of the teachers have nothing to do with the level of passing of the students from tertiary down to elementary. These suggest that the teachers' profile is not sufficient indicator to measure the academic performance of the students. Students performance is a product of socio-economic, psychological and environmental factors (www.scribd.com/doc/facotrs-affecting-students-performance/3.11.09/8:20)

Table 29
The Relationship Between the Owners/Administrators' Profile and their Extent of Researchers and Publications Conducted

Research and Publication Profile	r	Analysis of r	T-Test of Significance	Interpretation
Age	0.116	Slight correlation, almost negligible relationship	0.9841	Not significant accept Ho ³
Civil Status	0.3529	Slight correlation, definite but small relationship	3.1781	Significant, reject Ho ³
Monthly Income	-0.0736	Slight correlation, almost negligible relationship	-0.6219	Not significant, accept Ho ³
Educational Attainment	0.2936	Slight correlation, definite but small relationship	2.588	Significant, reject Ho ³
University/College Graduated	0.2866	Slight correlation, definite but small relationship	2.5207	Significant, reject Ho ³
Length of Service	0.3171	Slight correlation, definite but small relationship	2.8173	Significant, reject Ho ³

The relationship between the owners'/administrators' profile and the extent research and publications conducted is shown in table 29. As can be seen, the variables age and monthly income were found to have a slight correlation but negligible relationship. The t-test of significance revealed a not significant relationship, meaning age and monthly income of the owners/administrators have no relationship with their extent of research and publication conducted. The other profile variables such as civil status, educational attainment, university/college graduated and length of service were found to have a slight correlation but small relationship with their extent of research and publication conducted. The test of significance revealed that these variables have significant relationship with their extent of research and publication conducted. The hypothesis therefore is rejected.

Table 30
The Relationship Between the Owners'/Administrators' Profile and their Participation in Extension Services and Community Outreach Programs

Extension Services and Community Outreach Programs	r	Analysis of r	T-Test of Significance	Interpretation
Owners/ Administrators Profile				

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

Age	0.273083	Slight correlation, definite but small relationship	2.391958	Significant, reject Ho4
Civil Status	0.333833	Slight correlation, definite but small relationship	2.984122	Significant, reject Ho4
Monthly Income	0.1305	Slight correlation, almost negligible relationship	1.109097	Not significant, accept Ho4
Educational Attainment	0.3765	Slight correlation, definite but small relationship	3.424426	Significant, reject Ho4
University/College Graduated	0.339333	Slight correlation, definite but small relationship	3.039626	Significant, reject Ho4
Length of Service	0.316167	Slight correlation, definite but small relationship	2.808114	Significant, reject Ho4

The relationship between the owners'/administrators' profile and the extent of participation in extension and community outreach programs is presented in Table 30.

There was a slight correlation but small relationship with the variables age, civil status, educational attainment, university or college graduated and length of service. The assumption that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the owners/administrators and their extent of participation in extension and community outreach program is rejected. For the monthly income of the owners/administrators, it was found to have a slight correlation but negligible relationship. The computed t-test of significance indicates that there is no significant relationship between the monthly income of the owners/administrators and their extent of participation in extension and community outreach programs.

The age, civil status, educational attainment, school graduated and length of service of the owners/administrators have something to do with their interest in participating in extension and community outreach programs. Attached to the variables age, civil status and length of service are the responsibility the owners/administrators have an effect in their interest to conduct and participate in such programs. Likewise the educational attainment and school graduated from could have an influence in their interest and perceptions.

Table 31

The Difference between the Owners'/Administrators' and Teachers' Perceptions on the Factors for the Proliferation of Private Schools in Marawi City

Factors	T-Test Computed Value	Critical Value of T at .05	Interpretation
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Religious	0.5403	1.960	No significant difference, accept Ho5
Cultural	1.5252	1.960	No significant difference, accept Ho5
Social	1.6008	1.960	No significant difference, accept Ho5
Economic	0.9847	1.960	No significant difference, accept Ho5
Political	0.4875	1.960	No significant difference, accept Ho5

This suggests that collaboration between the owners/administrators and teachers are possible towards the attainment of quality education and in the realization of the mission, vision, goals and objectives of the schools. According to Fulan (1994) as cited in www.ncrel.org/3.13.09/11:45, schools are likely to be more successful in achieving in-depth learning when leaders work with the teachers and the community to build a collective educational vision that is clear, compelling, and connected to teaching and learning. This collective vision helps focus attention on what is important, motivates teachers and students, and increases the sense of shared responsibility for student learning. Schools with educational missions give educators stronger motivation and provide parents with a clearer picture of what the school values. Schools can get side-tracked toward non-productive programs, a focus on control, and uncoordinated decisions particularly when those schools serve large proportions of at-risk students. A clear vision and a common mission that identify the kind of learning to be achieved can help keep the school and the efforts of its staff and students on target.

The concerted opinion towards these factors could also mean that both owners/administrators and teachers are viewing the purpose of education in the same direction. This is also a good sign of possible teamwork for them in the improvement and success of their schools.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The private schools are operating legally, securing permit/licenses form authorized agencies and initially established as a foundation. The curricula adopted commonly have similarities. Inspired by the global trend on the Islamization of knowledge and with the success of the pioneering integrated schools in the area, newly established schools prefer the integrated curriculum in an attempt to excel in both fields of science and religion. Islam as a religion and way of life is made as an integral part of all subjects taught. Private schools in Marawi City are offering programs of study in all levels. Based on previous observations and the facts gathered in this study, even small schools offer complete programs.

The schools' type of building is influenced by the preference of the people of Marawi City to build concrete houses designed for maximum protection. The sizes of the classrooms are designed to accommodate not more than 50 students.

Status and proliferation of private schools in Marawi city ...

School facilities, equipment and services such as classrooms, blackboards and chairs are available and functioning very well while others such as toilets, water supply, working tables, canteen, library, guidance services, computers, reading corners were also available and functioning fairly well. Clinics with medical attendant, sports complex, cooking equipment and sewing equipment were either missing and or functioning poorly.

Instructional materials such as cardboards/flashcards, materials for project development, globe, map, atlas and posters, audio visual aids and books were available and functioning fairly well. Other instructional materials like computer assisted instruction, magazines, newspapers, journal and articles, sports equipment, laboratory equipment and musical instruments were very limited and were functioning poorly.

The schools' major sources of funds are the tuition fees and subsidy from the government.

The school owners/administrator respondents of the private schools in Marawi City were 41-50 years old while the teachers were mostly 20-30. Both owners/administrators and teachers were married and receive a monthly income of P10,000 and below. The owners/administrators have master's units while the teachers were mostly college graduates and were graduates of a university. The owners/administrators had 6-10 years services while the teachers have rendered less than a year only.

Lecture is still the most commonly used teaching strategy by the teachers in the private schools.

The factors of the proliferation of private schools in Marawi City were based on the religious, cultural, social, economic and political as strongly agreed by the school owners and administrators as well as the teachers. It is therefore concluded that the above factors have influenced the increase in numbers of the private schools in Marawi City.

Private schools of Marawi City always comply with governments requirements particularly in securing permit/licenses to operate, inspection and renewal.

The students of private schools have a very satisfactory performance in standardized and board examination from tertiary to the elementary level.

Though rarely conducted and participated in, the private schools of Marawi City were more inclined to literary publication and science researches.

Among the many extension and community outreach programs, culture and arts preservation as well as security /peace and order programs interest the respondents more.

The profile of the private schools and their compliance with government requirements has no relationship as well as the teachers' profile and the level of passing in appropriate standardized examinations while the owners/administrators profile has a relationship with the extent of researches/publications and participation in extension or community outreach programs.

The owners/administrators and teachers do not differ in their perceptions on the factors for the proliferation of private schools.

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